

Analyses of Environmental Effects on Secret Key Exchange in UAVs using Experimental Data

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Abstract—Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) play a significant role in modern applications ranging from surveillance to enabling communication in disastrous and remote areas, especially in Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs). Secure communications between UAVs and ground users are requisite, with secret key exchange being an important candidate for the physical layer security of such security protocols. This paper investigates the environmental factors influencing the efficacy and reliability of secret key exchange in UAVs, utilizing experimental data to draw insights. Through a series of field experiments, we analyze the effects of UAV structure and antenna location on the robustness of key exchange mechanisms. Our results indicate that certain environmental conditions, particularly adverse weather and noise introduced by the UAV body structure and propellers, do not impair the key exchange process. This research contributes to developing more security-resilient UAV communication systems, ensuring the reliability of communications links across diverse environments.

Index Terms—Non-Terrestrial Networks, Physical Layer Security, Secret key Exchange.

I. INTRODUCTION

Traditional wireless Terrestrial Networks (TNs) have the capability to blend infrastructure-based security with infrastructure-less security. However, applying infrastructure-based security to Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs) wireless communications proves impractical, necessitating alternative solutions. One promising approach is Physical Layer Security (PLS), where the physical layer, encompassing random channel gain and Channel State Information (CSI), is harnessed for enhanced security. Securing the physical layer helps mitigate potential information leakage scenarios from illegitimate users, safeguarding the link from compromise. The information-theoretic principles of secrecy, stemming from Claude Shannon's early contributions to communication theory [1], find relevance in securing communication systems. While Shannon focused on symmetric key encryption systems, Wyner's exploration of the wiretap channel marked a notable advancement in this field [2]. At present, there are primarily three methods to ensure PLS: an information-theoretic approach, a Signal Interference plus Noise Ratio (SINR) or keyless approach [3], and a key-based approach. The idea of exchanging secret keys based on channel characteristics was initially explored in [4]. Subsequently, the process evolved to consider circuit noise and external factors like interference, making the gen-

eration of secret keys more realistic and validated in real-world scenarios [5]. The PLS-based Secret Key Generation (SKG) involves four subprocesses: (i) channel probing, (ii) quantization, (iii) reconciliation, and (iv) privacy amplification. In this process, the channels between legitimate users are probed and utilized for sampling and quantization to generate random bits. As the channel is common and considered highly correlated in a coherence time, the random bits generated will also be highly correlated when following the reciprocity principle. In the event of a bit error, a key mismatch may occur. To minimize this probability, a reconciliation step is performed, followed by privacy enhancement measures. The key exchange scheme should guarantee both (a) the generation of secure keys with high entropy according to information theory and (b) the reconciliation of any errors between the private keys generated by the transmitter and receiver to ensure their identity.

Exploiting the reciprocity principle for PLS-based random SKG, researchers have been exploring various channel parameters to enhance mathematical and algorithmic models. In [5], secret keys for legitimate users were generated based on the envelopes of broadcasted signals, while Mathur et al. [6] introduced a novel quantization algorithm utilizing Level-Crossing Rate (LCR). After quantization, reconciliation follows to address bit mismatches that occurred during the quantization of secret keys. This step can utilize error detection protocols, such as the one proposed by Brassard and Salvail in [7], or error correction protocols, such as polar code [8] and Low-Density Parity Check (LDPC) [9] as channel coding methods. However, approaches based on both error correction and error detection protocols can also be combined to enhance Bit Mismatch Probability (BMP) [10]. Furthermore, an adaptive system among BBSS, Cascade, Bose–Chaudhuri–Hocquenghem (BCH) code, and Turbo code has been presented in [11], which is based on the comprehensive reconciliation efficiency index. Recently, an idea has been presented regarding the one-way secret key agreement analytically with a consideration of an active eavesdropper in the networks [12]. Apart from the above-mentioned approaches, a few ideas based on the zero-reconciliation or reconciliation-less approaches have also been presented in [13]. However, these concepts have only been identified in the literature within the context of body sensor network applications.

Similarly, massive Multiple-Input-Multiple-Output (mMIMO) remains the center of attention when it comes to addressing users' demands with hardware impairments. Presently, Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RISs) are considered a low-cost solution using dynamic uncontrollable features of wireless communications to improve the Quality-of-Service (QoS) and overall link reliability [14]. However, oxygen absorption at higher frequencies and frequent hand-offs of the users are conceivable tradeoffs. In 6G, Non-Terrestrial Wireless Communication Networks (NTWCNs), also known as NTN, are considered in integration with conventional TNs to enhance the connectivity specifically for high-speed users and on-demand and epoch requirements such as in catastrophe-stricken areas, remote areas, and bottleneck scenarios [15]. An NTN works in different layers, in which satellites can communicate directly to ground or sea users, or Uncrewed Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) provide connectivity as Aerial Base Stations (ABSs) or relays. A RIS-aided communications model is given in [16] using a tethered UAV relaying from a Base Station (BS) to a RIS, which is analyzed for the indoor and outdoor deployment of the RIS.

Nevertheless, the coalescence of TNs with NTNs addresses connectivity by providing virtual Line-of-Sight (vLoS); however, it also exposes the users to security risks. Conventionally, information is secured on each layer of Open-System Interconnection (OSI) layers with the help of hardware infrastructure and software algorithms. Alternatively, in NTNs, due to a lack of infrastructure, seamless security can be provided using the physical layer of wireless communications. The authors in [3] proposed an optimized SINR-based secrecy rate. In this article, we present an analysis of the UAV effect over PLS-SKG. We used four use cases during the experiment using Alta-X and DGI hexa-copter UAVs.

This paper is further organized as follows: Section II describes the system design and the setup to carryout the measurement tests. Initially, the system was tested from ground to rooftop communications followed by four use cases of UAVs communication. Finally Section III presents the conclusion.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

The system is designed to take measurements of the UAVs using a Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) N200 kit as a receiver, an Edison LTE HDMI modulator with a single DVB-T [17], and log periodic antennas [18] that are used on both ends of the communications link. The USRP kit was further connected to a laptop, and LabView Software was installed [19]. The data was gathered using the Inphase-Quadrature (IQ) form. The post-processing is carried out using Matlab 2022a on the core i7 system. In LabView, a model has been created to obtain and record the IQ data into a file using Algorithm 1. Initially, the system was tested without a UAV to validate the model, and an antenna was mounted on top of the building, and one was installed 1 meter above the ground. Then, it was tested on UAVs using four different antenna placement configurations, discussed in the subsections.

The HDMI Modulator with a single DVB-T output has a robust encoding system designed for high-performance multimedia processing. At its core, the encoder features a 200MHz 32-bit Reduced Instruction Set Computer (RISC) host Center Processing Unit (CPU), ensuring efficient handling of complex tasks. Accompanying this is a dedicated 200MHz 32-bit security processor for enhanced data protection and a 200MHz 32-bit audio processor to manage audio encoding seamlessly. The modulation capabilities are equally comprehensive, with an output frequency range of 174-to-233MHz in Very High Frequency (VHF III) and 470-858/790 MHz in Ultra High Frequency (UHF) with Long Term Evolution (LTE)-ON, both with 50Ω input and output impedance. It supports various Forward Error Correction (FEC) rates, guard intervals, and offers constellation choices of QPSK, 16QAM, and 64QAM. The Radio Frequency (RF) output level is adjustable from a default $90\text{dB}\mu\text{V}$ up to $+6\text{dB}\mu\text{V}$ or down to $-14\text{dB}\mu\text{V}$ in 2 dB steps. With bandwidth specifications of 7MHz for Very High Frequency (VHF) and 8MHz for Ultra High Frequency (UHF), Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) modes of 2K and 8K, Reed Solomon error correction, and symbol rates up to 31.668 MBPS, the modulator ensures high signal quality with a Modulation Error Ratio (MER) exceeding 35 dB. This combination of advanced processing power and flexible modulation makes the HDMI Modulator an efficient and reliable solution for high-quality transmissions.

The USRP kit is a high-performance software-defined radio device that features a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) to enable a wide range of real-time wireless communications signal processing. The robust design and integration capability with daughterboards to support more frequency ranges make it ideal for research, prototyping, and development in wireless communication. While using USRP, we also have an option of using Blade-rf on UAVs as published in [20]; however, the powerful FPGA and the extension with daughterboards to operate on different frequency ranges and efficient filtering ability gives an edge to USRP over blade-rf.

Both devices, i.e., USRP and Modulator, were connected to the same log periodic antennas with dimensions of $262\text{ mm} \times 170\text{ mm} \times 1\text{ mm}$, having 25 dipoles with 74.5 mm longest dipole and 6.5 mm shortest dipole. This antenna has been tested for measurement using Signal Hound SA44B in an indoor scenario using a portable spectrum analyzer [21] and on a customized UAV [18].

In our study, the communication channel between two nodes in the system is characterized using different fading models to represent the real-world conditions encountered in UAV communications. Specifically, the channel between UAVs, denoted as h_i , is modeled using Rice fading, which accounts for the Line-of-Sight (LoS) component in aerial communication links. This model is appropriate due to UAVs' relative elevation and movement patterns that often ensure a dominant direct path between communicating nodes. Conversely, the channel from rooftop transmitters to ground receivers can be modeled using Rayleigh fading, depending upon reflections of the multipath propagation environment where LoS is often

Algorithm 1: Record IQ Data from USRP N200

```
1 Initialize Front Panel Controls:
2  $f_c \leftarrow 700 \times 10^6$  // Set Center Frequency
3  $F_s \leftarrow 1 \times 10^6$  // Set Sample Rate
4  $G \leftarrow 20$  // Set Gain
5  $S_R \leftarrow \text{False}$  // Set Start Button
6  $S_S \leftarrow \text{False}$  // Set Stop Button
7  $S_i \leftarrow \text{"Ready"}$  // Status Indicator
8 Initialize USRP Device:
9 USRP Session  $\leftarrow$  USRP Open.vi
10 Configure Signal Parameters:
11  $f_c \leftarrow$  Value from Front Panel
12  $F_s \leftarrow$  Value from Front Panel
13  $G \leftarrow$  Value from Front Panel
14 Call USRP Configure.vi // Center
    Frequency, Sample Rate, Gain
15 while  $S_S$  is not True do
16 | IQ Data  $\leftarrow$  USRP Read.vi
17 | Call Write to File.vi with IQ Data
18 | Update  $S_i \leftarrow$  "Data Acquired"
    end
19 Close USRP Device:
20 Call USRP Close.vi
21 Error Handling:
    if error occurs then
22 | Update  $S_i \leftarrow$  "Error"
    end
```

Fig. 1. Rooftop to ground communication

obstructed, and non-LOS components dominate. This dual-model approach allows for a realistic simulation of the varying conditions in different communication network segments. The experimental environment was kept stable and unchanging throughout the tests to ensure the reliability and consistency of the results, thereby allowing for a realistic assessment of the communications performance under the specified fading conditions.

A. Ground – rooftop

We conducted a test for communication from the ground to the rooftop in the presence of environmental external factors, such as trees located approximately 20 meters from

the receiver antenna and 5 to 10 meters from the transmitter antenna. The height of the receiver antenna from the ground was 16.2 meters, and the height of the transmitter antenna was 1.2 meters above the ground and placed over the wooden box, as shown in Fig. 1. The distance from the box to the building was 14 meters, while the receiver antenna was connected to a two-meter rod to extend it from the roof, shown in Fig.1(c), which made the separation distance between communicating antennas approximately 19 meters, sketched in Fig. 3. The geometry of this setup is given in these conditions, and the communication channel exhibits characteristics of a Rician fading model. This is because the communication scenario involves a dominant LoS path between transmitter and receiver, especially in a ground-to-rooftop setup. However, the presence of the trees and other environmental effects introduces additional multipath components due to reflections, scattering, and diffraction, which are typical in Rician fading channels. The LoS and multipath components received can be modeled as Y and mathematically can be expressed as,

$$Y = L + y_1 + jy_2, \quad (1)$$

where L is the LoS component and y_1 and y_2 are the Gaussian independent and identically distributed (i.i.d) Random Variables (RV) with zero mean and σ^2 variance as in the non-LoS components. The Probability Density Function (PDF) of the Rician RV is represented as Y can be written as,

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{y}{\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{y^2 + L^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) I_0\left(\frac{yL}{\sigma^2}\right), \quad (2)$$

where $I_0(\cdot)$ is Bessel function of its first kind with zeroth order. Eq. 2 can also be expressed in terms of Rician factor K and $K = \frac{L^2}{2\sigma^2}$, where L is the LoS power component and $2\sigma^2$ is the power of non-LoS components.

The magnitude of the received signal and the PDF of the measured data are plotted in Matlab, as shown in Fig. 2. Nevertheless, due to the specific geometry and distances, the communication involves significant reflections from the ground and trees when the transmission is from the rooftop and received on the ground. The PDF of the Rician fading channel follows a Rayleigh model at -40 dB gain and a Gaussian distribution at 15 dB [22].

B. UAV-to-UAV

A few tests were conducted with the setup mounted on the UAV, and tested with antenna placement at different locations on the UAVs to check the response of the UAVs' structure over the received signal. The tests were conducted in Herning, Denmark, and in a flying arena in Silkeborg, Denmark. The UAVs used during the test were Alta-X and DJI Matrice 600 Pro. The Alta-X UAV boasts impressive specifications and is designed for versatile aerial operations. Its physical dimensions make it a formidable platform, with an unfolded diameter of 1415 mm (excluding props) and 2273 mm (including props), providing a stable footprint for various payloads. When folded, the UAV's compact diameter of 877 mm enhances portability. The height of the Alta-X is 387 mm,

(a). Magnitude of Received Signal

(b). Distributions of measured data and simulated data

Fig. 2. Magnitude and probability distribution of the measured signal

Fig. 3. Geometry of measurement setup

extending slightly to 434 mm in the Skyview configuration, indicating its adaptability for different flight profiles. The UAV operates on a custom PX4 flight control stack, supporting various flight modes such as manual, altitude hold, position, mission, loiter, orbit, and return-to-home, catering to manual and automated flight requirements. The standard typical empty weight of an Alta-X UAV is 10.86 kg and can carry up to 15.06 kg payload. Similarly, The DJI Matrice 600 Pro hexacopter is a robust aerial platform engineered for professional applications, featuring a diagonal wheelbase of 1133 mm, contributing to its stable flight characteristics. When fully unfolded with propellers, frame arms, and GPS mount extended (including the landing gear), the UAV measures a substantial 1668 mm \times 1518 mm \times 727 mm, making it suitable for carrying heavy payloads and sophisticated sensors. In its folded state, with the propellers, frame arms, and GPS mount compacted (excluding the landing gear), the UAV's dimensions reduced to 437 mm \times 402 mm \times 553 mm, enhancing its portability and ease of transport. The Matrice 600 Pro, equipped with six TB48S batteries, weighs approximately 10 kg, providing a solid foundation for stable and extended flight operations. The hexacopter is designed to handle a maximum recommended

TABLE I
ANTENNA PLACEMENT ON UAVS

Antenna Location on UAV	Keyword
Alta-X antenna installed up and DGI antenna installed up	Up-Up
Alta-X antenna installed up and DGI antenna installed down	Up-Down
Alta-X antenna installed down and DGI antenna installed up	Down-Up
Alta-X antenna installed down and DGI antenna installed down	Up-Down

takeoff weight of 15.5 kg. During the rest of the paper, keywords like up-down will be used according to the Table I.

In carrying out the tests, we maintain the distance between UAVs to be 19 meters with 23 meters of height. In one of our experiments, the height with almost no reflections from the ground was around 33 meters. However, due to bad weather conditions and low temperatures, we conducted our tests over 23 meters in height. The Alta-X UAV was in auto-pilot mode (programmed for), and the DJI UAV was manually controlled. The height and separation distance was ensured during the experiments, as shown in Fig. 4. While carrying out this experiment, different power levels were used, from -15 dBm to 15 dBm. The PDFs of the received signal for different power levels are plotted using (2), as illustrated in Fig. 5, validating the same angle of arrivals in all cases. The main concern of these experiments is to check the effects of fluctuations in received signals introduced by the UAV's body over the SKG. The secret key generation method used during this process was the thresholding method. We obtained the IQ data during the measurements and validated the quantization algorithm over the measured data.

To validate and examine the effects introduced by the UAVs' propellers on SKG, we take four cases into consideration. We initially installed the antennas above the propellers on

Fig. 4. Antenna placement configuration on UAVs

Fig. 5. PDF of the angle of arrivals for different power

Fig. 6. Correlation vs success rate for different antenna placement

both the UAVs and collected the IQ data, and similarly, the process was repeated for down-down, up-down, and down-up configurations. After the collection of data, we extracted 60 samples (S_i) from the received IQ samples (Y) using a thresholding mechanism. The sample exceeding the threshold which is taken as the mean value of the extracted samples. The sample value of i th index was compared with the mean value of S and was considered 1 above the mean, and for below, it was considered 0, mathematically can be represented as,

$$Q(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } S_i > \text{mean}(S), \\ 0, & \text{if } S_i < \text{mean}(S), \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

After conducting a series of tests with various antenna placement configurations on UAVs, our analysis focused on the relationship between the key success rate and the correlation factor. We found that there was no significant effect on secret key generation when varying the antenna's physical location on the UAV. Initially, at lower correlation factors, the key agreement process experienced noticeable disruptions due to increased noise levels. However, as the correlation factor increased, we observed a marked improvement in the success rate of key generation, leading to a smoother and more efficient

key agreement process. The Fig. 6 shows the relation between the correlation coefficient.

The detailed examination of our data, highlights that while the graph in Fig. 6 shows a positive correlation between the correlation factor and the success rate, there are subtle variations among different antenna placement configurations which are hard to analyze. These differences, though minor, were noticeable in the zoomed-in view of the results. Upon further investigation, we determined that these slight variations could be attributed to the differing weather conditions during the tests. Specifically, the up-up and down-down configurations were tested in snowy weather, the up-down configuration in cloudy weather, and the down-up configuration in sunny weather. This variation in environmental conditions likely influenced the results, contributing to the observed discrepancies between antenna placement configurations.

The SKG rate is typically higher in non-stationary scenarios because the channel variations are more frequent and dynamic, providing more bits/nats of entropy over time. The fast fading and varying multipath due to movement create a richer source

of randomness, allowing for more rapid key generation. For the Rician fading channels, even with a strong LoS component, movement can introduce sufficient variations in the non-LoS components to increase the SKG rate. The agreement ratio is always higher when there is a higher correlation factor, resulting in easy prediction by the illegitimate user. Hence, it is highly recommended to use SKG in high-mobility scenarios, such as moving UAVs in NTN wireless communications. The dynamic nature of the channel mostly introduced by movement, increases the entropy and the rate at which keys can be generated. However, in the stationary scenario, artificial noise or interference can be introduced to maximize the entropy and make the channel harden.

III. CONCLUSION

We investigated the impact of antenna placement configurations on physical layer-based secret key generation in UAV-enabled communication networks. It has been demonstrated that variations in antenna placement, whether from rooftops or among UAVs, did not significantly influence the effectiveness of secret key generation. This reinforces the robustness of physical layer security as a viable solution for ensuring secure communication in non-terrestrial networks where traditional infrastructure-based security approaches are not feasible. Future research should explore the impact of different environmental conditions and advanced antenna technologies on physical layer security to further enhance and adaptive security measures for diverse operational real-world scenarios.

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